

Framing of Oil Spillage and Gas Flaring in Rivers State in Three Selected Nigerian Newspapers

Ata-Awaji Anthony Reuben

Department of Mass Communication
Topfaith University, Mkpatak, Akwa Ibom State
Email: aa.reuben@topfaith.edu.ng
<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-9750-8092>

Nyerhovwo Muoboghare

Department of Mass Communication
Delta State University, Abraka
Email: nyerhovwo.muohoghare@yahoo.com
<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-3458-1332>

Bassey Victor Ikot-Osin

Department of Mass Communication
University of Nigeria, Nsukka
Email: victor.bassey@unn.edu.ng
<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-9124-7184>

Soibi Oruwari

Department of Media & Journalism Studies
University of Port Harcourt
Email: soibioruwari@gmail.com
<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-6858-8757>

Etimbuk E. Obot

Institute for Legislative Studies, Abuja
Etimbuk.obot@nils.gov.ng
<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-9317-1575>

Emmanuel Omula

Department of Mass Communication
Topfaith University, Mkpatak, Akwa Ibom State
Email: e.omula@topfaith.edu.ng
<https://orcid.org/0009-0004-8450-8369>

Theresa I. Linus

Department of Mass Communication
Topfaith University, Mkpatak, Akwa Ibom State
Email: tessylinus77@gmail.com
<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-1320-9934>

Peace Nwamaka Ojonta

Department of Mass Communication
University of Nigeria, Nsukka
Email: peace.ojonta@unn.edu.ng
<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-1267-8165>

Simon Reazanyi Sheyigari

Department of Mass Communication
Federal University Lokoja
sheyigarireazanyi@gmail.com
<https://orcid.org/0009-0003-6789-7211>

Abstract

Background: Oil spillage and gas flaring constitute some of the environmental pollutions confronting humanity, especially in oil producing countries and communities, like those in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. This situation affects aquatic and human lives, with economic, social and health consequences. Amid these consequences, communication scholars are unanimous about the efficiency of framing of an issue such as oil spillage and gas flaring by the mass media on policy making and salvaging of situations.

Objective: The study aimed at ascertaining how *Punch, Vanguard and Daily Trust* newspapers framed oil spillage and gas flaring in Rivers State, from January 2022 to December 2023.

Methods: The study adopted content analysis as its research design, thus studying 504 editions of the newspapers selected through composite week sampling. The code sheet served as the instrument for data gathering.

Result: The study found that opinions of experts on oil spillage and gas flaring in Rivers State were not given serious attention by the *Punch, Vanguard, Daily Trust newspapers*. The study has shown that geo-political depiction of Nigerian newspapers does not influence their framing of oil spillage and gas flaring, rather their editorial policy.

Contribution: The study concludes that a more scientific approach to framing of environmental pollution in Nigeria has not been given serious attention to by newspapers in the country.

Unique contribution: This study provides empirical evidence for understanding newspaper framing of environmental issues.

Key recommendation: Nigerian newspapers should place importance on the opinions of environmental experts, as this will ensure that a more scientific approach is taken to framing oil spillage and gas flaring in the country.

Keywords: Flaring, Framing, Gas, Newspaper, Oil Spillage

Introduction

God entrusted humans with the responsibility of caring for the planet's environment when he created it. "The Lord God took the man, and put him in the Garden of Eden to till it and keep it." This charge is contained in (Reversed Standard Version of the bible, 2:15). God designed humans to live in harmony with the environment and to do all in their power to ensure its continued viability and prosperity. God granted humans dominion over everything else He made, according to Okwueze (2024), who shares this belief. Unfortunately, many people have given up on the responsibility of preserving and caring for the environment, preferring instead to appease, conquer and plunder it.

Over time, the environment has suffered due to humankind's insatiable need to discover and use natural resources for material and social gain. Okwueze (2024) agrees with this view and emphasises that humans' desire to reside in natural areas just for their own benefit has persisted in endangering the ecosystem. Pollution of the natural environment is a major problem for people the world over. The United Nations General Assembly placed a high priority on addressing environmental insensitivity, and in 1984, established the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED) to formulate a worldwide strategy for fostering a more environmentally conscious activity. Because of its pervasiveness, environmental contamination has inspired both national and international initiatives to combat the issue. While environmental degradation had been a source of worry prior to 1984, the WCED's action served as a catalyst for renewed focus on the issue and added a scientific component to the ongoing fight. This is due to the fact that in 1985, for instance, ministers from various African countries met in Cairo, Egypt, to discuss and agree on measures to combat environmental degradation throughout the continent. All of the aforementioned endeavours were made with the goal of maintaining a healthy environment.

The plea for a healthy and sustainable environment has gained more voices in recent times. Humans' continued hostility toward the natural world has rendered it hazardous, notwithstanding these initiatives and strategies. All of Nigeria's environmental contamination originates in the Niger Delta. According to Okoro and Nnaji (2012), environmental pollution is a major issue in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. It has a devastating effect on the earth. Oil spillage in Aletto-a community in Eleme Local Government Area of Rivers State, as reported by the *Punch Newspaper* of June 15, 2023, destroyed farmlands and left many fishermen stranded. Residents of Eleme Local Government Area of Rivers State reported that the Okuru River, which flows through Aletto, Akpajo, Agbonchia and Ogale, was polluted by an oil spill that began at a manifold operated by an oil company. This incident happened four months after a comparable one in the Ebubu community. The residents of Bodo community in Rivers State's Gokana Local Government Area also cried out due to similar incident in 2022. The problem persists in spite of outcry of the people.

Amid this, communication experts hint that newspapers are effective at framing issues. Newspapers and other mass media, they argue, shape public opinion and potential policy responses by framing situations. Ndinojuo *et al.* (2018) assert that in order for the masses to understand a situation, the media must first emphasise certain features of it. Thus, frames are constructed to enhance understanding of issues. Similarly, Reuben and Ikot-osin (2020) assert that the mass media play significant roles in the societal watch in all forms. The news media exercised such responsibility based

on the prevailing societal circumstances. One of the responsibilities of the mass media, as espoused by Harold Lasswell in 1948, is surveillance of the environment. Cookey (2024) argues that the issue of environmental contamination and remediation efforts can be amplified by the news media by reporting issues pertaining to the environment.

Therefore, this study explored how the *Punch, Vanguard and Daily trust newspapers* framed the situation from January 2022-December, 2023. Oil spillage and gas flaring are considered because, in comparison to other issues, such as indiscriminate waste disposal, which poses minor health risks, and annual flooding, which only affects a small number of people in Rivers State, oil spillage and gas flaring constitute multifarious problems.

Research Objective

The aim of this study is to examine how *Punch, Vanguard and Daily Trust* newspapers framed oil spillage and gas flaring in Rivers State. Precisely, the objectives of this study centred on the need to:

- 1 Determine the prominence given environmental pollution in Rivers State by the *Punch, Vanguard and Daily Trust* newspapers in their reportage; and
2. Examine the major sources of environmental pollution stories covered by the newspapers under study in Rivers State.

Literature Review

Media Framing

One of the ways in which the news media can influence how significant events are seen is through the use of framing (Ezegwu, 2021). Ogbodo et al. (2021) state that the metaphor of frame is utilised in order to provide an explanation for the structure and presentation of information that is seen in news stories. According to Batta et al. (2013), the way in which an individual thinks about and comprehends a story is directly proportional to the perspective that the mass media utilise. These scholars add that frames provide an explanation of the context of the problem, its roots and potential solutions. It has been pointed out by Ndinojuo et al. (2018) that the idea of framing news has been utilised in a free and liberal manner to relate to concepts such as the topic, the context, the frame of reference, or the angle of approach to the news. In the course of their reporting, journalists give their stories significance by stating a particular news value that establishes a connection between one incident and other happenings that are similar. There are many different types of framing devices that Ndinojuo et al. have offered for the purpose of describing and analysing news frames. Some examples of these framing devices include headlines, subheadings, images, logos, photo captions, leads, sources, quotes, pull quotes, charts, statistics, and concluding comments.

We are able to draw the conclusion from the reviews that media framing is the process by which journalists deliver stories in a manner that invites readers to engage in critical thinking about specific situations and to take informed decisions about those situations. It is therefore not sufficient to only trigger thought; it must also provide a rationale for the audience to behave in response to the information provided by the news media.

Literature Review

Boyagoda (2016) states that the definition of environmental communication provided by Development Cooperation and Environment (DCE) is the planned and strategic utilisation of communication processes and media products with the purpose of facilitating public involvement,

the implementation of sustainable projects and the formulation of successful policies. What environmental communication is all about is the utilisation of communication strategies for the purpose of conserving, protecting and promoting the environment pertaining to human beings. According to Nwabueze (2015), human's environment consists of everything that is external to him, including his interactions with other objects. Thus, environmental communication, as argued by Bashir (2013), is a method that is both fundamental and practical for gaining an understanding of the environment and humans' role within it.

According to Asadu (2012), environmental communication includes techniques such as public awareness campaigns, education and involvement of the masses. The purpose of these strategies is to encourage individuals to contemplate the consequences of their activities and how the management of natural resources may benefit both individuals and the planet. In Rivers State, this approach has the potential to reduce pollution. According to the findings of Ono et al. (2023), it would appear that nature and nurture are in conflict with the physical environment on a global scale. The majority of environmental damage in the West is attributed to natural sources, whereas in Nigeria, pollution is primarily caused by human activity. As a result, Rivers State's ecology has progressively worsened and become one of the most polluted in Nigeria, as stated by Worika and Etimire (2018).

As pointed out by Umunnakwe and Aharanwa (2016), oil spills, which can occur both on land and in water, have the potential to cause significant damage to the environment as well as the flora and fauna that live there. It is the release of oil or liquid petroleum hydrocarbon into the aquatic environment, such as oceans and coastal waterways, as well as on land. It is mostly caused by human activity, which includes the exploration and transportation of oil.

It is not surprising that environmentalists in the Niger Delta region are concerned about the impact that gas flaring will have on the ecosystem of the region and the lives of people who live in the surrounding area. Consequently, newspapers and other forms of mass media, are being utilised in order to educate the general public about the dangers that are associated with environmental contamination. According to Sandman *et al.*, cited in Okunna and Omenugha (2022), newspapers have continued to be effective media for disseminating news to a wide number of people. In spite of the fact that broadcast media are readily available to the general public, a sizeable section of the population continues to rely on newspapers to satisfy their information requirements. Nwala et al (2024) maintain that newspapers can bring to the attention of the general public, oil companies and the government, environmental damage that has been caused by oil exploitation in the Niger Delta.

Empirical Review

Ekeanyanwu and Nwosu (2022) investigated the role that print media play in environmental activism by analysing the coverage of pollution in newspapers in Rivers State. The purpose of this study was to investigate the impact that the print media have on environmental conservation efforts in Rivers State by conducting an analysis of the coverage of themes linked to pollution. The Port Harcourt Telegraph, Rivers Voice and Garden City Times were the newspapers utilised for the purpose of analysing items that were published between 2019 and 2021. The rigorous sampling of

the selected newspapers for the study focused mostly on articles that discussed environmental contamination as its principal topic of interest. In order to make sense of the data, quantitative analysis was utilised, and a mixed-method approach was also adopted in order to identify the frame kinds and frequencies. According to the findings of the study, numerous media outlets portrayed environmental pollution as a matter of who was to blame, with a particular emphasis placed on the roles that oil companies and government agencies had in the problem. Following the findings of the study, it was determined that human interest stories were successful in bringing awareness to the suffering of affected population and in evoking feelings of empathy.

Odoemelam et al. (2021) investigated the impact of framing by analysing the coverage of oil contamination in newspapers from 2014 to 2018. The time period covered was from 2014 to 2018. The objective of this study was to examine the different ways in which three newspapers-the *Daily Sun*, the *Guardian*, and the *Punch* newspapers-present information about environmental pollution in the Niger-Delta region. The purpose of this comparison was to identify the different frames that were utilised in the coverage of oil pollution in the region. A content analysis approach was adopted as the research design for the study. The *Daily Sun newspaper* was shown to have a higher prevalence of human interest frames compared to the *Guardian and the Punch newspapers*. This is followed by morality framework, accountability, conflict, and economic ramifications. Although scholars from both inside and outside of Nigeria have investigated the issue of oil spills and gas flaring in Rivers State, none of their studies have taken into account the coverage of oil spillage and gas flaring that the *Punch, Vanguard and Daily Trust newspapers* received between January 2022 and December 2023. More so, all of the earlier studies had distinct objectives from the current one. The purpose of this current work is to fill that gap in the existing body of literature.

Theoretical Framework

Framing Theory

The 1974 work of Erving Goffman, titled *Framing Analysis: An Essay on the Structure of Experience*, is often cited as the foundation of framing theory, according to Lamidi and Olisa (2016). These scholars point out that the media use framing to promote a certain understanding of a problem by choosing which issues to highlight, which ones to leave out and how to elaborate on them. To back up the previous claim, Ogbodo et al. (2021) state that Sociologist-Erving Goffman first proposed the concept of framing theory in 1974, with its roots in Gregory Bateson's work. The idea provides an explanation for how people's experiences are structured in their minds. According to this theory, which is relevant to the fields of journalism and communication studies, journalists use certain strategies when reporting the news (p.158). According to Nwafor et al. (2017), the theory posits that people who ingest media messages can make sense of new information by using the frames that the media adopted. The implication is that journalists use metaphorical picture frames to contain the ever-changing subject of events and activities, drawing our attention to some topics, concepts and people while ignoring or downplaying the rest.

Methodology

The research design used for this study is content analysis. It was considered appropriate for this study because, Ohaja (2003) contends that this research design allows the analysis of manifest content of communication to discover the pattern existing therein. Adelekan (2014) states that out of more than 100 publications in Nigeria, around 17 have a nationwide readership. The *Punch*,

Vanguard and Daily Trust newspapers were chosen from among seventeen national newspapers. The three national dailies were selected because of their large readerships and extensive circulations. From January 2022 through December 2023, a total of 365 issues were published by each of these three publications, which gave us a total of 2,190 issues. Every newspaper would put out 365 issues within 24 months. Hence, 2,190 issues would be published by the three publications. The sample size was determined using the composite week sampling technique. We assumed that there would be 24 weeks spanning January 2022–December 2023, in accordance with the recommendation made by Wimmer and Dominick (2011) that a study could use a random selection of one Monday (from the four or five possible Mondays in the month), one Tuesday (from the available Tuesdays), and so on, until every weekday has been taken into account. Also, since there are seven days in a week, that equates to seven study days every month. All three of the newspapers were covered by the chosen dates. As a result, there will be 168 editions of each newspaper over two years (7 X 24). A total of 504 newspapers were included in the sample, which was obtained by multiplying this figure by 3. Data was generated by the researchers using coding sheets. To ensure reliability of the instrument, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient, through test and re-test approach was used. The empirical calculation of result showed the correlation of (r) of 0.99. This also showed a high correlation, thus the instrument had strong reliability. This study used quantitative methods to analyse its data. Cartoons, letters to the editor, features, editorials, and plain news items are the units of analysis for this study.

Results

Three newspapers were studied. These newspapers were studied from January 2022-December 2023. Total editions of paper studied was 504. The research had access to the five hundred and four editions of the four newspapers, coded them and content analysed.

Table 1 shows prominence accorded oil spillage and gas flaring in Rivers State by the studied newspapers

Newspaper	Prominence		
	Front Page	Inside Page	Back Page
<i>Punch</i>	2	17	0
<i>Vanguard</i>	0	13	0
<i>Daily Trust</i>	0	14	0
Total	2	44	0

Source: Field Work 2024

Of the 19 occasions the *Punch Newspaper* reported the oil leak and gas flaring in Rivers State, just two times (as shown in Table 1) were featured on the main page. From this, we inferred that the front page of the newspaper featured just 10.52% of the items about the oil leak and gas flaring that were covered, while the remaining 17.47% were covered internally, since the issue did not receive any coverage on the back page. There was no framing of the situation on the front page of the *Vanguard newspaper*. There were thirteen instances of oil spills and gas flaring in Rivers State that were covered by the *Vanguard newspaper*, however they were only published on the inside pages of the newspaper. Similarly, the *Daily Trust newspaper* did the same thing. None of the newspapers frame the scenario on the back page. This implies that none of the newspapers ascribe prominence to oil spillage and gas flaring in Rivers State. Further implication is that the

environmental pollution in Rivers State would not receive the desired attention from government and other stakeholders because as noted by Ogu (2020) one of the ways of giving priority attention to the environment is by giving environmental issues prominence in frequent reportage of events by the mass media.

Table 2 shows major sources of environmental pollution stories covered by the newspapers under study in Rivers State

Newspaper	Sources of News	Event-Based (Beat Reporting)	Victim/ Eye Witness Account	Press Release	Organisations	Experts on the Environment
<i>Punch</i>		9	5	3	2	0
<i>Vanguard</i>		6	4	1	2	0
<i>Daily Trust</i>		9	2	1	1	1
Total		24	11	5	5	1

Source: Field Work 2024

Table 2 shows that the three newspapers in Rivers State primarily used event-based reporting when crafting stories about the oil spill and gas flaring. After then, the accounts of victims and witnesses are presented, with different newspapers using different sources of information (press releases and organisations) to frame the scenario. Meanwhile, just one percent of the news sources for the *Daily Trust newspaper* were environmental experts. Reports about the oil leak and gas flaring in Rivers State were framed by the *Punch and Vanguard newspapers* based on events, eyewitness accounts, press releases, and organisations, rather than the opinions of environmental specialists. Therefore, it may be inferred that neither *Punch nor Vanguard newspapers* bothered to seek the opinion of specialists on the oil leak and gas flaring in Rivers State, whereas reporters for the *Daily Trust newspaper* did so to a lesser extent. It follows that the *Punch and Vanguard newspapers'* editorial policies did not value professional opinion on the matter. Because of this, the general public will not have access to information based on scientific studies and expert opinions regarding the issue.

Discussion of Findings

As contained in table one, oil spillage and gas flaring were covered by the three newspapers 46 times. However, only one of the newspapers featured the issue on its front page twice. As a result, just 4.34 percent of the stories made it to the homepage. That the newspapers studied gave little attention to the environmental disasters caused by oil spills and gas flaring in Rivers State, is evident from this severely insufficient coverage. The findings of Okoro and Nnaji (2012), who examined the coverage of environmental contamination in the Niger Delta by the *Guardian, Vanguard, Daily Sun, and ThisDay newspapers*, match with these results. Despite an increasing amount of environmental concern on a worldwide scale, the study found that the mass media studied, did not favourably feature articles about pollution in the Niger Delta.

The data from Table 2 shows that most of the stories about environmental pollution in Rivers State that were reported by newspapers were based on events or beat reporting. This is followed by the accounts of victims and witnesses, with different newspapers using different sources of

information (press releases and organisations) to frame the scenario. The *Punch and Vanguard newspapers* did not base their coverage of the oil spillage, leak and gas flaring in Rivers State on the opinions of environmental experts, while *Daily Trust newspaper* relied on them as a source for only 1% of its story.

Conclusion

Nigerian media have ignored the oil spill and gas flaring in Rivers State. Consequently, the issues were not given much attention in the newspapers studied. This is despite the seriousness of the situation. More so, geo-political depiction of Nigerian newspapers does not influence their framing of environmental pollution, rather their editorial policy. This conclusion is drawn because of the three newspapers studied, two (*the Punch and the Vanguard newspapers*) are from Southern Nigeria yet framing of oil spillage and gas flaring in these newspapers was poor. So, oil spillage and gas flaring in Rivers State did not receive noticeably different levels of coverage in the *Punch, the Vanguard, and Daily Trust newspapers*. Nigerian newspapers have not covered oil spills and gas flaring using a more scientific methodology. This is because opinion of experts on the environment constituted only one per cent of news sources for framing of oil spillage and gas flaring in Rivers State. Once again, the principles of framing theory have been validated by the conclusions obtained from the findings of this study. Consider that lack of newspapers framing of the oil spillage and gas flaring in Rivers State prevented the matter from receiving the attention it deserved from policymakers and the government. This is due to the fact that news framing undeniably directs public attention and thought toward a specific subject (Mu'azu and Moses, 2021).

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Prominence should be given to oil spillage and gas flaring in Rivers State because of their consequences on human and aquatic health, social and environmental consequence, etc.
3. Importance should be placed on opinion of experts on the environment by Nigerian newspapers. This will ensure that a more scientific approach is given to the framing of environmental pollution in the country.

References

- Adelekan, I.O. (2014). The Nigerian press and environmental information for sustainable development. *Local Environment*, 14 (4). 297–312.
- Asadu, C.A. (2012). *Anatomy of communication for development*. Choba: University of Port Harcourt Press.
- Batta, H.E, Ashong, C.A & Udousoro, N.W. (2015) Examining environmental discourses on energy utilisation in select Nigerian newspapers. *Developing Country Studies*, 5 (16), 40-51.
- Bashir, A. (2013). Communication of climate change issues. In D. Wilson & H. Batta (Eds.). *Science, Health and Environmental Communication Global and Local Perspectives*, 281-333, Global Ventures.
- Boyagoda, E.W.M.S. (2016) Reporting green: An exploratory study of news coverage of environmental issues in Sri Lankan Newspapers. *Proceedings of second Asia Pacific*

- Conference on Contemporary Research*. Retrieved from www.apiar.org.au on July 24, 2024.
- Cookey, P. (2024). Communication in mitigating the effects of plastic waste for a clean and healthy environment. In Danie, P.U and Mbazie, S (Eds) *Issues and trends in communication and development a festschrift on Professor Christopher, Ifeakachukwu Ochonogor*, 196-206. Port Harcourt: Custom Publishing.
- Ekeanyanwu, N. T., & Nwosu, P. C. (2022). The role of print media in environmental advocacy: Analysing newspaper coverage of pollution in Rivers State. *Journal of Media Studies*, 9 (2), 67 – 89.
- Ezegwu, D.T. (2021). Framing of sexual crimes by select Nigerian newspapers. In N. T. Ekeanyanwu (Ed.). *The Nigerian Journal of Communication*, 18 (1 & 2), 169-179.
- Holy Bible King James Version. New York: HarperCollinsPublishers.
- Lamidi, I.K. &Olisa, D.S. (2016). Newspaper framing of the APC change mantra in the 2015 Nigerian presidential election: A study of the Punch, and the Guardian newspaper. *Journal of Communication and Media Research*, 8 (2), 201-217.
- Ndinojuo, B.E., Ihejirika, W.C.& Okon, G.B. (2018). Reinvigorating the framing theory: Appraising reports on Nigerian military and Boko Haram insurgency. *International Journal of Media, Journalism and Mass Communications*, 4, (4), 10 – 19.
- Nwabueze, C. (2015). *Environmental communication perspectives on green communication and information management*. Owerri: Topshelve Publishers.
- Nwala, B, Okure, E.G, Otonnah, H.C & Onwugbuta, C.U. (2024). Content analysis of environmental degradation activities in the Niger Delta region. In Daniel, P.U & Mbazie, S. (Eds) *Issues and trends in communication and development a festschrift on Professor Ch ristopher Ifeakachukwu Ochonogor*, Port Harcourt: Geocilia Integrated Services LTD, 153-162.
- Nwafor, K.A., Nwasum, C.J.& Nkwuda, J.I. (2017). One country, two eras: Analysis of how three Nigerian newspapers framed President Goodluck Jonathan and MuhammaduBuhari's economic policies. *The Nigerian Journal of Communication*, 14 (1), 197-223.
- Odoemelam, C.E., Hasan, N.N & Hussein, A. (2021) The Effects of Framing on Oil Pollution as Covered by Print Media: A Case Study of Nigerian Newspapers. *Romanian Journal of Communication and Public Relations*, 23 (1), 1-22.
- Ogbodo, J.N., Ugbo, G.O., Duru, H.C.&Jibrin, S. (2021). Newspaper framing of the 2019 Nigerian presidential election. *The Nigerian Journal of Communication*, 18 (1 & 2), 152-168.
- Ogu, E.C. (2020) Environmental journalism and sustainable national development in Nigeria: An Analysis. *IMSU Journal of Communication Studies*, 4 (1), 163-173.
- Ohaja, E.U. (2003). Mass communication research and project report writing. Lagos: John Letterman Ltd.
- Okoro, N. & Nnaji, G. O. (2012). Press coverage of environmental pollution in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria: A content analysis of the *Guardian, Vanguard, Daily Sun and Thisday* Newspapers. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3, (2), 34-46.
- Okunna, C.S & Omenugha, K.A. (2021). *Introduction to mass communication* (3rd edition). Enugu: New Generation Educare LTD.
- Okwueze, M.I (2024). Religion, socio-economic forces, politics and environmental sustainability. In the book of abstract for 2024 Hybrid International Conference, organized by the

- Department of Religion and Cultural Studies, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, on the theme: Religion, Politics, And Environmental Sustainability
- Ono, G.N., Edegor, O., & Ezegwu, D. (2023). Achieving better environment through development communication in Onitsha and environs of Anambra State. *ACCE Book of Abstract*.
- Reuben, A.A. & Ikot-Osin, B. (2020). Exploring advocacy journalism among News Editors against soot and indiscriminate disposal of solid waste in Port Harcourt. *Nnamdi Azikiwe University Journal of Communication Studies*, 1 (1), pp.162-176.
- Umunnakwe, J. E. & Aharanwa, B.C. (2016). The impact of oil spillage on soil and health of Idu-Ekpeye Community, Port Harcourt. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Engineering Science and Technology*, 3 (7), 1569-5176.
- Wimmer, R. and Dominick, J. (2011). *Mass media research: an introduction*. Wadsworth: Cengage learning.
- Worika, I.L & Etemire, U. (2020). Environmental Sustainability and Regulation in Rivers State, Nigeria. *Chinese Journal of environmental law*, 4, 71-96.